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THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING ARITHMETIC OPERATIONS IN THE PRIMARY GRADE

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Annotation: This article discusses the procedure for performing arithmetic operations. It also discusses the role and importance of didactic games in teaching arithmetic operations in primary school.

Key words: Mathematics, elementary school, student, teacher, arithmetic operations, didactic game, quality of education.

The formation of a well-rounded person remains one of the pressing issues facing our society today. The young generation sitting in school today is our successor, the one who will take over our work tomorrow, continue our lives, and pass them on to the next generation, the owners of the great future of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to reconsider educational areas and specialties in the general education system from the perspective of today's students. We should also focus on the widespread introduction of new information and pedagogical technologies into the educational process, increasing our attention to teachers who are dedicated to raising our children as complete human beings, and in short, raising the education system to a completely new level in terms of quality. Therefore, the introduction of pedagogical technologies that fully meet the requirements of the time into all subjects, especially mathematics lessons, is one of the requirements of the present era.

It is known that play plays a central role in the activities of a child who takes his first steps on the threshold of school. Playing is their favorite pastime, and they try to combine any activity with playing. Therefore, the teacher should increase the effectiveness of the educational process by using it appropriately, without crowding out their favorite pastime - play. Play is a certain part of a child's life. Through play, the child establishes contact with the environment, natural phenomena, landscapes, objects, plants, and animals.

Some non-traditional lesson forms in which didactic game technologies are implemented

Formulalar darsi – o'quvchilarning formulalarni puxta o'zlashtirishlari bo'yicha turli o'yinlar shaklidagi mashqlar o'tkazish darsi.

Formulas lesson - a lesson in which students conduct various game-like exercises to help them master formulas.

Kim oshdi savdosi darsi – o'quv fani ayrim bo'limi bo'yicha bilimlarni har bir o'qituvchi qanchalik ko'p bilishini namoyish etish darsi.

The auction lesson - a lesson to demonstrate how much knowledge each teacher has in a particular subject area.

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Yarmarka darsi – dars mavzusini bo‘laklar bo‘yicha oldindan o‘zlashtirgan o‘quvchilarning o‘zaro muloqot asosida sinfga qiziqarli tushuntirish orqali o‘tiladigan dars.

A fair lesson - a lesson that is taught to the class through an interesting explanation based on interaction between students who have previously mastered the topic of the lesson in parts.

“Tergovni bilimdonlar olib boradi” darsi - dars mavzusini oldindan puxta o‘rgangan o‘quvchilar yordamida qiziqarli savol-javoblar, tahlillar asosida isbotlab tushuntirish mashqlari bo‘lib, bunda o‘quvchilar dars mavzusini o‘zlashtirib, eslab qolishlari uchun qulaylik yaratiladi.

The lesson "Investigation is conducted by knowledgeable people" - a series of interesting question-and-answer, analysis-based, and explanation exercises with the help of students who have thoroughly studied the lesson topic in advance, which helps students master and remember the lesson topic.

Integral (integratsiyalashgan) darsi - bir necha fanlarga oid integratsiyalash uchun qulay bo‘lgan mavzular bo‘yicha tashkil qilingan dars bo‘lib, o‘quvchilarning turli fanlarga qiziqishlarini ortirib, ta’lim jarayonidagi faolliklarini ta’minlaydi. Bunday darslar o‘quvchilarga fanlararo bog‘liqlikni o‘rgatish orqali ulardan olam tuzilishining ularning ilmiy asoslarini to‘liq idrok etish, ilmiy dunyoqarashlarini shakllantirish, ijodiy tafakkurlarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

An integrated lesson - a lesson organized on topics that are convenient for integration across several subjects, which increases students' interest in various subjects and ensures their active participation in the educational process. Such lessons help students to fully understand the scientific foundations of the structure of the universe, form a scientific worldview, and develop creative thinking by teaching them intersubjectivity.

“Mo‘jizalar maydoni” darsi – o‘quvchilar bilan o‘tkaziladigan qiziqarli o‘yin bo‘lib, turli savollarga belgilangan vaqt davomida to‘g‘ri javoblar topish va g‘oliblarni rag‘batlantirish orqali o‘quvchilarda fikrlash, topqirlik, ziyraklik va bilimlarini kengaytirib borish sifatlarini shakllantiradi.

The "Field of Wonders" lesson - an interesting game with students that develops the qualities of thinking, resourcefulness, intelligence, and expanding their knowledge by finding the correct answers to various questions within a set time and encouraging the winners.

Conditions for the practical application of didactic games

Didaktik o‘yinlarni tanlashda ishtirokchilarning yoshi, bilimi va tarbiyalanganlik darajasi hisobga olinadi. Har bir didaktik o‘yin mashg‘ulotlariga o‘ziga xos xavfsizlik talablari qo‘yiladi. When choosing didactic games, the age, knowledge, and level of education of the participants are taken into account. Each didactic game activity has its own safety requirements. Full compliance with these safety requirements should be the constant focus of every organizer. In addition, it is necessary to correctly

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determine the amount of time spent on each didactic game, know the specific principles of compliance, and apply them in accordance with the purpose of the lesson.

The didactic games below can be used to teach arithmetic operations in primary grades.

“Silent” game

In this game, cards with numbers written on them are hung on the board. The main condition of the game is that all students sit quietly, and according to the conditions of the game, the results are recorded according to the operation of addition or subtraction.

In the place where the cards are placed, they place cards with the sum of 2 or 12 written on them, as a result of their addition or subtraction.

“Kara Scholars” game

This game can be organized in different ways. You can also use cards like the one above. Or the teacher can check the results of the multiplication table in the form of “yes” or “no”.

For example:

$$4*5=20 - \text{yes} \qquad 8*6=46-\text{no} \qquad 5*7=35- \text{yes}$$

$$5*6=29 - \text{no} \qquad 9*4=36 - \text{yes} \qquad 7*9=63- \text{yes}$$

Through these games, it is possible to achieve results in effectively organizing the lesson process and reinforcing a new topic.

Didactic games affect the child's emotions, instilling in him a positive attitude and interest in learning. Children participate in the game with great pleasure. They eagerly await the start of the game, their minds involuntarily conjuring up a joyful image of tomorrow’s school day.

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